

Combining isotopic and elemental tracers for enhanced sediment source partitioning in complex catchments

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Abstract

Sediment fingerprinting has the potential to elucidate and quantify soil erosion processes by assessing the provenance of sediments in water bodies. In this regard, several types of tracers have been used to discriminate different sediment sources. Stable isotopic composition of fatty acids is associated with land use/vegetation cover, while elemental composition is related to different mineralogy. Isotopic tracers are characterised by their isotopic ratio and total content, requiring specific fingerprinting models. Consequently, this has led to few studies combining elemental and isotopic tracers.

In this context, our analysis focuses on the ability of merging isotopic and elemental tracers to distinguish sediment sources in an ungauged Mediterranean mountain catchment. This catchment is characterised by homogenous lithology, ephemeral streams, and a marked seasonality. It has experienced significant land use changes over the centuries, with rangelands being converted into croplands to boost agricultural production. However, this process was later reversed due to land abandonment in the middle of the twentieth century, allowing natural revegetation to take place. As a result, achieving optimal source discrimination in these complex landscapes poses a significant challenge, highlighting the importance of combining different types of tracers.

To explore this possibility, we collected composite source samples from three distinct land uses: cropland, Mediterranean forest, and pine forest, as well as two geomorphic features: degraded areas and channel banks. By considering these diverse sampling locations, we aim to capture the variability in sediment sources within the catchment. Our dataset spans one full hydrological year, allowing us

31 to analyse sediment dynamics throughout different seasons and hydrological events. By integrating
32 isotopic and elemental tracers, we aim to improve the identification and quantification of sediment
33 sources in this intricate catchment setting.

34 First, the Conservative Balance (CB) method was applied to integrate isotopic ratio and total
35 content of each fatty acid into a single weighted tracer. A substantial improvement of source
36 discrimination was observed when combining the weighted fatty acid (WFA) and elemental
37 composition tracers, compared to their individual usage. Evidence from this study supports the
38 application of different types of tracers when achieving effective discrimination becomes challenging.

39 The apportionment results revealed that agriculture, channel banks, and subsoils were the primary
40 contributors, accounting for an average contribution of 29%, 39%, and 30% respectively, across most
41 seasons. In contrast, sediment sources characterized by more permanent vegetation cover and
42 minimal human influence, such as the pine afforestation and the Mediterranean forest, exhibited
43 negligible contributions during the studied year. The findings suggest that agricultural practices in
44 Mediterranean agroecosystems, coupled with storm events, play a significant role in the catchment
45 hydrodynamics and subsequently sediment export. Additionally, severe soil loss originating from
46 degraded areas, despite their relatively small coverage, contributes significantly to the overall
47 sediment dynamics.

48 By unravelling the hydrological implications of these sediment sources, our study provides
49 valuable insights into the interplay between land use, hydrological processes, and sediment dynamics
50 in Mediterranean mountain catchments.

51

52 **Keywords:** Suspended sediment, catchment hydrodynamic, tracer combination, conservative
53 balance method, sediment source discrimination

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55

56 1. Introduction

57 The identification of hotspot areas for sediment sources is crucial in recognizing the triggering
58 factors behind the export of fine-grained sediment to streams, where hydrological processes and
59 human activities play a crucial role (Boix-Fayos et al., 2017; Owens, 2020). Inappropriate
60 management practices are responsible for land degradation and the subsequent export of soil sediment
61 and associated nutrients (Ramos et al., 2022). To identify areas prone to erosion and delineate hotspot
62 regions, sediment fingerprinting and spatially distributed erosion models are widely used (Borrelli et
63 al., 2021; Collins et al., 2020). However, even though both methods can be considered
64 complementary, distributed models provide spatial information from areas where erosion is more
65 likely to occur, but they do not inform about the origin of sediments exported to water courses (Lizaga
66 et al., 2022). Contrary to spatially distributed models, sediment fingerprinting techniques deliver
67 information on the origin of sediment. The technique aims to quantify the sediment contribution from
68 each potential source to the mixture or target sample using a variety of tracer properties and
69 quantitative models. However, while sediment fingerprinting has been widely implemented, there
70 still exist open questions regarding the conservative behaviour of tracers, source discrimination
71 power, and especially the tracer selection methods (Evrard et al., 2022). Recent research evidenced
72 that the use of different methods for selecting tracers could substantially modify the apportionment
73 results affecting both Bayesian and Frequentist models (Palazón et al., 2015b; Pulley et al., 2015;
74 Cooper and Krueger, 2017). Other authors devised methodologies to complement fingerprinting
75 studies and developed methods to identify non-conservative, non-consensual, and non-consistent
76 tracers (Lizaga et al. 2020; Latorre et al., 2021). The purpose of these methods is to assess the impact
77 of each individual tracer on the fingerprinting model outputs and determine whether multiple
78 solutions exist within a dataset when applying either Frequentist or Bayesian models for un-mixing.
79 Multiple distinct solutions may arise when working with overdetermined systems characterised by
80 more than $n - 1$ tracers, being n the number of sources (e.g. 3 sources and 3 or more tracers).

81 To increase discrimination power and expand the number of potential sources, the use of different
82 types of tracers has been promoted. A wide range of soil properties has been used as fingerprinting
83 tracers during the last decade, such as elemental composition (Ballasus et al., 2022; Derakhshan-
84 Babaei et al., 2022; Dhivert et al., 2022; Liang et al., 2023; Tsyplenkov et al., 2021; Wynants et al.,
85 2020; Zhang et al., 2021), fallout and lithogenic radionuclides combined with stable elements (Navas
86 et al., 2020; Szalińska et al., 2021; Navas et al., 2022; Palazón et al., 2015a; Gaspar et al., 2019),
87 especially ^{137}Cs (Evrard et al., 2020), magnetic properties (Ramon et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020)
88 and UV–VIS wavelength absorbance (Lake et al., 2022). However, these properties are mostly not
89 suited to discriminate between different land uses (Hancock and Revill, 2013; Chen et al., 2016). For
90 this reason, plant-specific isotopic signature of organic molecules such as fatty acids (FA) have been
91 proposed for identification of land-use-specific sediment export (Glaser, 2005; Gibbs, 2008; Blake et
92 al., 2012; Alewell et al., 2016; Reiffarth et al., 2016; Mabit et al., 2018; Upadhayay et al., 2018a;
93 Riddle et al., 2022). Since its first use, several studies have implemented isotopes of long-chain fatty
94 acids. The technique has been applied in different environments and setups (Upadhayay et al., 2018b;
95 Lavrieux et al., 2019; Hirave et al., 2020; Lizaga et al., 2021).

96 When using isotopic tracers, the total tracer content is an essential variable that influences the
97 results (Upadhayay et al. 2017). Consequently, concentration-dependent isotopic mixing models are
98 necessary, which hinders their compatibility with elemental tracers. Recently, Lizaga et al. (2022)
99 developed a new physically-based framework, the Conservative Balance (CB) method, that combines
100 isotopic ratio and total content of each fatty acid into a weighted elemental tracer. The CB method
101 presents three benefits: it enables the analysis of isotopic tracers using classical fingerprinting models,
102 it allows the combination of isotopic and elemental tracers directly and, simultaneously, it enables
103 the implementation of advanced tracer selection methods which are key for a correct unmixing
104 process.

105 Although isotopic tracers have the potential to enhance discrimination among different land uses,
106 they may decrease the discrimination of sources lacking vegetation cover (Reiffarth et al., 2016;

107 Lizaga et al., 2021). Conversely, elemental composition tracers effectively distinguished geomorphic
108 features but exhibited limitations in discriminating between different vegetation covers. The main
109 shortcoming of the lack of discrimination is the need to combine or remove certain types of sources,
110 or avoid targeting them due to the impossibility of proper source discrimination. The resulting need
111 to exclude or merge sources could represent a limitation when targeting restoration practices, specific
112 vegetation types or geoforms. However, to the best of our knowledge, no study has dealt with a joint
113 implementation of isotopic and elemental tracers to test their ability to discriminate land covers and
114 geomorphic features.

115 To fill this gap, a dataset composed of the stable isotopic composition of long-chain fatty acids,
116 and elemental composition tracers has been considered to assess the main factors leading to sediment
117 transport during one hydrological year in a mountain Mediterranean catchment with agroforestry
118 practices. Within this context, our analysis and evaluation encompass the following objectives: i)
119 examining the information provided by elemental and isotopic tracers, ii) assessing the impact of
120 combining both tracers, and iii) investigating the primary sources of sediment in relation to rainfall
121 events, land use management, and agricultural activities throughout one hydrological year.

122

123 2. Material and methods

124 2.1 Study area

125 The study area is a medium size catchment of 23 km² located in the northern-central part of the
126 Ebro basin, Spain, with the Barués village in its centre (Fig. 1). An ephemeral stream tributary of the
127 Arba River drains the catchment. The mean annual temperature is 13°C, while the mean annual
128 precipitation ranges between 550 mm to 650 mm (recorded since 1929 at the Yesa reservoir;
129 AEMET). The climate is characterised by cold winters and hot and dry summers when the main
130 streams can dry up. In the last century, the catchment has suffered intense changes in terms of land
131 use and human pressure, varying from agricultural dominance during the 1960s to less than 16%

132 nowadays (Lizaga et al., 2018a). At present, most of the catchment is occupied by different vegetation
133 covers, with the Mediterranean open forest (MF) and the pine afforestation monoculture (PI) being
134 the predominant types. These covers are interspersed with each other, creating a mosaic habitat with
135 a patch dynamic. The MF occupies 60% of the area, while the PI covers 20% of the area. The
136 remaining 16% is designated as cropland. The Mediterranean forest primarily consists of trees from
137 the *Quercus* family, specifically *Quercus robur* L., *Quercus coccifera* L., and *Quercus ilex* L., as well
138 as scrublands and grasslands. The pine forest, on the other hand, is primarily composed of *Pinus*
139 *halepensis* Mill., with the main crops being winter cereals such as *Triticum aestivum* L. and *Hordeum*
140 *vulgare* L.

141 The soils are alkaline with low organic carbon content and a secondary accumulation of
142 carbonates, mainly classified as Calcisols and Cambisols (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) (Lizaga
143 et al., 2019b). The different land uses have predominant silt texture with similar percentage of sand,
144 silt and clay fractions in both the topsoil and deep soil (Lizaga et al., 2018a).

145 Most of the rainfed agricultural land is located on fluvial terraces occupying the valley floors and
146 the areas close to the streams with gentle slopes (Lizaga et al., 2019a). The valley floor is infilled by
147 eroded sediment from the surrounding slopes and appears deeply incised, especially in the middle
148 and lower parts of the catchment where its thickness reaches its maximum of up to 5 m. The stream
149 channel banks (CB) are mainly composed by silt-dominated colluvium sediment characterised by
150 steep banks without vegetation cover. On the contrary, natural vegetation is located at the highest
151 altitudes, increasing its density from the medium altitudes where the croplands were abandoned in
152 the last years to the upper part where abandonment occurred decades ago. This results in a vertical
153 and horizontal multi-strata canopy structure. Combined with this pattern, the afforestation forest
154 (*Pinus halepensis* Mill.) predominates in most upper Northern parts. The most important crops are
155 winter cereals (*Triticum aestivum* L. and *Hordeum vulgare* L.) with some patches of rapeseed
156 (*Brassica napus* L.). Sowing takes place between October and November, and the harvest season is
157 from mid-May to July.

158 The precipitation amount was recorded with a one-minute frequency at the study site using a
 159 tipping bucket rain gauge connected to an Em50 Decagon data logger. However, some gaps are
 160 present in the temporal line due to technical issues. For this reason, data from the Yesa weather station
 161 (30T ETRS89 X:648317 Y:4719912, altitude: 487 m.a.s.l), located 20 km north of Barués, were
 162 extracted and combined to complete the observed gaps. Previous to the data filling, the relationships
 163 between both databases were assessed with an r coefficient of 0.71.

164

165

166 *Figure 1. Location of the Barués catchment in the central part of the Ebro Basin (NE Spain). 3D map of the catchment and*
 167 *its surroundings. A-E pictures of the different land use, A) agricultural land use occupying the valley floors and deeply*
 168 *incised stream surrounded by landslides (topples), B) Mediterranean forest, C) pine afforestation, D) degraded soil, E) river*
 169 *bank, and F) eroded crop after a high intensity rainfall.*

170

171 2.2 Sample collection and analysis

172 The potential sediment sources and sediment sampling locations established in this study were
 173 identified during reconnaissance surveys following previous research conducted in the catchment
 174 about hydrological connectivity and coupling (Lizaga et al., 2018b), changes in soil properties after

175 land abandonment (Lizaga et al., 2019b) and ^{137}Cs estimates of spatial soil redistribution rates (Lizaga
176 et al., 2018a).

177 A total of 130 source samples were collected from the main land uses present in the study
178 catchment. From these, 20 were from cropland (AG), 63 from Mediterranean forest (MF), and 15
179 from pine afforestation (PI). To analyse the contribution of the main geomorphic elements, 32 source
180 samples were collected from eroded subsoil (SS) areas and main stream channel banks (CB). To
181 evaluate sediment export, suspended sediment collector samples (SSC) were collected following the
182 methodology proposed by Phillips et al. (2000) in the middle part of the stream at the outlet of the
183 catchment. The suspended sediment samples were integrated per three months, and collected as close
184 as possible to the end of each climatological season, during one entire year, from June 2017 to June
185 2018. The objective of the sampling schedule was to provide a close replication of the suspended
186 sediments transported during each season for evaluating both seasonality and intra-seasonal effects
187 of the crop practices such as sowing, fertilising and harvesting in the sediment contribution to the
188 streams.

189 Following the predominant silt-loam texture of the soils in the catchment (Lizaga et al., 2021) and
190 the most widespread methodology (Owens et al., 2016), both mixture and source samples were air-
191 dried, ground, homogenised and sieved to $\leq 63\mu\text{m}$ particle size. The relationships between tracers and
192 the size fractions support that $\leq 63\mu\text{m}$ fraction compile the range of variation for most of the study
193 tracers.

194 The stable elements and magnetic susceptibility were analysed in the 130 source samples and
195 sediment mixtures. The compound-specific stable isotopes (CSSI) were analysed for a total of 40
196 source samples and for all the sediment mixtures. A total of 35 tracers were analysed to ensure a
197 variety of fingerprints for characterising the sources and the sediment mixtures. Elemental
198 composition (mg kg^{-1} , Al, As, Bi, Ca, Cr, Cu, Fe, K, Li, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Ni, Pb, P, Rb, Se, S, Sr, Ti,
199 Tl, V, Zn) was analysed by ICP-AES after total acid digestion pursued in two cycles with HF (48 %),
200 HNO_3 and H_2O_2 and a second cycle with HNO_3 , HCl, and Milli-Q water in a microwave oven. The

201 mass-specific magnetic susceptibility was measured using a Bartington Instruments dual-frequency
202 MS2B sensor in 10 ml samples at low (0.47 kHz; χ_{lf}) and high (4.7 kHz; χ_{hf}) frequencies. For this
203 study, we use the mean value of three measurements at the low frequency χ_{lf} ($10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$).

204 Lipids were extracted from the soil and sediment (source) and suspended sediment (sink mixture)
205 samples using accelerated solvent extraction (Dionex ASE 350, Thermo Scientific, Bremen
206 Germany) with dichloromethane (DCM): MeOH (9:1 v/v) at 100°C and 13 MPa in three cycles of 5
207 min (30 mL cells, 60% flush volume). For this c.a. 3 g of dried sample was weighed in 22 mL stainless
208 steel cells to which a recovery standard was added (12.5 ng C17:0 FA, dissolved in 50 μL ethyl
209 acetate). The recovered C17:0 was used to compute the FA content of the soils and sediments. The
210 lipid extract was dried using rotary evaporation (CentriVap, Labconco, Kansas City, USA) at 60°C
211 and 20 mbar. Lipid fraction was re-dissolved in DCM/Isopropanol (2:1 v/v) before being separated
212 in neutral and acid fraction using aminopropyl solid-phase extraction columns (Bond Elute, 500mg,
213 6mL, Agilent Technologies) according to [Blake et al. \(2012\)](#). Neutral fraction was removed with
214 DCM/Isopropanol after which the acid fraction was eluted using 2 % acetic acid in diethyl ether
215 ([Russell and Werne, 2007](#)). After taking the acid fraction to dryness by rotary evaporation, the fatty
216 acids were methylated using Methanolic BF_3 (14 %, 20 min at 60 °C).

217 The obtained fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were quantified after the addition of an internal
218 standard (C19:0 FAME), using capillary gas chromatography (GC Trace Ultra, Thermo scientific)
219 with flame ionisation detection (FID) equipped with a 5% Phenyl Polysilphenylene-siloxane column
220 (BPX5, 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm , Trajan). After adapting the solvent volume for optimal
221 concentration for compound-specific stable isotope (CSSI) analysis, the ^{13}C abundance of the
222 individual FAME was determined using GC-isotope ratio mass spectroscopy (GC-IRMS). The GC-
223 IRMS system used consisted out of a Trace 1310 GC equipped with the same GC column as for GC-
224 FID connected to an ISOLINK II through a CongFlo IV to a Delta-V advantage IRMS detector (All
225 Thermo scientific). Normalisation of the ^{13}C signal on the Vienna Pee Dee belemnite (VPDB) scale
226 was performed by injecting a mixture of C14:0, C16:0, C18:0 C20:0 and C30 FAME, and C14:0,

227 C16:0, C18:0 C20:0 fatty acid ethyl ester provided by Arndt Schimmelmann (Indiana University),
 228 calibrated using NBS 19, and L-SVEC defined as exactly +1.95 and -46.6 ‰, on the VPDB scale,
 229 respectively, every five samples. Additionally, mixtures of fatty acids (C16, C17, C19 and C20) were
 230 methylated together with the samples to correct for the contribution of the methyl group of the FAME
 231 in order to obtain the isotopic ratios of the FA.

232

233 **2.3 Tracer selection methods and fingerprinting model**

234 An essential criterion for tracer selection methods is to exclude non-conservative tracers from
 235 being incorporated into the models, as their inclusion may lead to erroneous outcomes (Collins et al.,
 236 2017; Haddadchi et al., 2013; Owens et al., 2016; Smith and Blake, 2014). Some tracers fall outside
 237 the range of sediment source values due to their lack of conservativeness, sediment particle size
 238 effects or external factors such as contamination. Tracer selection is crucial for a successful unmixing
 239 and negatively affects all types of models, either Frequentist or Bayesian (Pulley et al., 2015; Cooper
 240 and Krueger, 2017; Lizaga et al., 2020a; Latorre et al., 2021).

241 Additional complexity arises from the joint analysis of isotopic ratios and scalar variables, such as
 242 the elemental composition. To this aim, the CB method has been implemented to combine the isotopic
 243 ratio and total content of each FA into a weighted tracer that contains the information of both
 244 variables. The detailed physical derivation of the CB method can be found in the original research by
 245 Lizaga et al. (2022). For the sake of simplicity, the CB method is briefly illustrated using the following
 246 equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \delta^{13}C = \frac{(^{13}C/^{12}C)}{(^{13}C/^{12}C)_{std}} - 1 = \frac{R}{R_{std}} - 1 \\ C \cong ^{13}C + ^{12}C \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

247

248 where C represents the carbon total content, R is the isotopic ratio ($^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ represents
 249 the relative difference of isotopic ratios from a standard reference. From the total carbon content (C)
 250 and the isotopic ratio (R) of a sample, the individual content of each isotope (^{12}C , ^{13}C) can be derived,
 251 being both descriptions equivalent.

$$\begin{cases} ^{12}\text{C} = \frac{C}{1+R} \\ ^{13}\text{C} = \frac{C \cdot R}{1+R} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

252 We now introduce a physical model involving two sediment sources with isotopic contents (C_1 , C_2)
 253 and isotopic ratios (R_1 , R_2) that are mixed into proportions (w_1 , w_2), under the constraint $w_1 + w_2 = 1$.
 254 The resulting isotope contents in the mixture ($^{12}\text{C}_M$, $^{13}\text{C}_M$) can be simply calculated by means of a
 255 weighted average.

$$\begin{cases} ^{12}\text{C}_M = w_1 ^{12}\text{C}_1 + w_2 ^{12}\text{C}_2 \\ ^{13}\text{C}_M = w_1 ^{13}\text{C}_1 + w_2 ^{13}\text{C}_2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

257 The first equation in [3], which constitutes the conservative balance of ^{12}C , can be written in terms
 258 of C and R using the first equation in [2].
 259

$$\frac{C_M}{1+R_M} = w_1 \frac{C_1}{1+R_1} + w_2 \frac{C_2}{1+R_2} \quad (4)$$

260 The second equation in [3], which corresponds to the conservative balance of ^{13}C , is expressed in a
 261 similar way using the second equation in [2].

$$\frac{C_M R_M}{1+R_M} = w_1 \frac{C_1 R_1}{1+R_1} + w_2 \frac{C_2 R_2}{1+R_2} \quad (5)$$

262 Both equations, [4] and [5], can be combined by substituting the first term in [4] into Eq. [5].

$$\left(w_1 \frac{C_1}{1+R_1} + w_2 \frac{C_2}{1+R_2} \right) R_M = w_1 \frac{C_1 R_1}{1+R_1} + w_2 \frac{C_2 R_2}{1+R_2} \quad (6)$$

264 The resulting equation [6] constitutes the conservative balance (CB) of an isotopic tracer and allows
 265 calculating the mixture isotopic ratio (R_M) without the need to consider its total content (C_M). As a

266 result, the proposed model retains its validity even when the mixture undergoes physico-chemical
 267 processes that may alter its total content while preserving the isotopic ratio.

268 Starting with Eq. [6], all the terms are shifted to the right side of the equality, and the proportions are
 269 factored out.

$$0 = w_1 \frac{C_1(R_1 - R_M)}{1 + R_1} + w_2 \frac{C_2(R_2 - R_M)}{1 + R_2} \quad (7)$$

270

271 The resulting equation [7] it is equivalent to the conservative balance of a virtual elemental tracer
 272 (T), combining the information of the isotopic ratio and the total content, with the following values
 273 in the sources (T_1 , T_2) and the mixture (T_M):

274

$$\begin{cases} T_1 = \frac{C_1(R_1 - R_M)}{1 + R_1} \\ T_2 = \frac{C_2(R_2 - R_M)}{1 + R_2} \\ T_M = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

275

276 Given the condition that $^{13}\text{C} \ll ^{12}\text{C}$ (or equivalently $R \ll 1$) in natural carbon, the precedent
 277 expression can be approximated and represented in terms of the measured variables (C , $\delta^{13}\text{C}$). Starting
 278 with Eq. [7], the numerators are expressed in terms of the relative difference of isotopic ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$)
 279 substituting the ratio definition, $R = R_{std}(\delta^{13}\text{C} + 1)$, from equation [1]. The denominators of Eq. [7] are
 280 then approximated under the condition $R \ll 1$ using $1 + R \cong 1$.

281

$$0 = w_1 C_1 R_{std} (\delta^{13}C_1 - \delta^{13}C_M) + w_2 C_2 R_{std} (\delta^{13}C_2 - \delta^{13}C_M) \quad (9)$$

282 The precedent equation is simplified, multiplying both sides of the equality by $1/R_{std}$, and finally
 283 expressed as the conservative balance of a virtual elemental tracer (T), obtaining an approximation of
 284 Eq. [8] under the condition that $R \ll 1$.

285

$$\begin{cases} T_1 = C_1(\delta^{13}C_1 - \delta^{13}C_M) \\ T_2 = C_2(\delta^{13}C_2 - \delta^{13}C_M) \\ T_M = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

286

287 After this transformation, the isotopic tracers are weighted to scalar quantities and it is possible to
 288 implement the Conservativeness Index (CI), Consensus Ranking (CR) and the Consistent Tracer
 289 Selection (CTS) methods together with the elemental composition tracers to i) extract the source
 290 apportionment predictions that each tracer introduces into the model and identify non-conservative
 291 tracers based on that information, ii) unravel the presence of multiple consistent solutions present in
 292 over-determined datasets (more or equal number of tracers than sources), and iii) assess the effect of
 293 combining elemental and isotopic tracers in source discrimination. CI is a non-parametric test that
 294 analyses tracer conservativeness using mixture and source data to create an index as a more
 295 sophisticated version of the range test. CR is a scoring function based on several random debates
 296 between tracers, in which the tracers preventing consensus are assigned low scores ([Lizaga et al.,](#)
 297 [2020a](#)). Consensus-reaching processes proceed in a convergent multistage way, where experts present
 298 their opinions and discuss and negotiate to bring positions closer by modifying their initial opinions
 299 ([Pérez et al., 2018](#)). In fingerprinting studies, the mentioned experts are the tracers in the dataset.
 300 CTS, similar to the DFA, identifies the most discriminant tracers, but it also examines their
 301 mathematical properties to ensure consistency in over-determined datasets (e.g., 3 sources and 3 or
 302 more tracers) ([Latorre et al., 2021](#)).

303 The CI index was adapted to better describe the conservativeness of tracers in a high-dimensional
 304 space of 5 sources. The predicted source contributions from each tracer were first calculated and

305 characterised by its centroid. Then, the CI index was calculated as the percentage of solutions with
306 conservative apportionments ($0 \leq w_i \leq 1$) relative to the centroid position. Thus, while obtaining a
307 similar tracer classification as the previous index, the new definition does not penalise those tracers
308 with dominant apportionments from one source and distributions close to a vertex of the physical
309 space. Despite the new implementation of the CI in the FingerPro R package, both the former and the
310 new definition are available for its comparison.

311 Based on the mathematical nature of the models, for five sources, a minimum of $n - 1$ tracers are
312 required (being n the number of sources) to obtain a determined system of equations with one possible
313 solution. Thus, a minimum of four tracers are required to unmix five sources. To implement the tracer
314 selection for unmixing, the methods mentioned above were used to remove those tracers with
315 apparently non-conservative or consensual behaviour and select an optimal set of tracers for each
316 mixture. The most discriminant quartet of tracers with a conservative solution extracted from the CTS
317 analysis was extended, incorporating consistent tracers from the dataset with a maximum error
318 threshold $\varepsilon = 0.03$. To estimate the relative contribution of each potential sediment source to the
319 mixtures, a Frequentist fingerprinting model implemented as an R package-FingerPro (Lizaga et al.,
320 2018; Lizaga et al., 2020b) was applied.

321

322 3. RESULTS

323 3.1 The role of each type of tracer and their synergy

324 To check the discrimination ability, the two types of tracers (weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA and elemental tracers)
325 were analysed individually and combined. In terms of source discrimination, Fig. 2a-c displays the
326 discriminant capacity of the considered weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracers ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs and FAs-content) using
327 linear discriminant analysis (LDA). The weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracers (WFA) LDA (Fig. 2a) displayed
328 good discrimination between the different land uses such as croplands (AG), Mediterranean forest
329 (Mf) and Pine afforestation (PI), but lower discrimination between the geomorphic features.

330 Contrary to the WFA tracers, the elemental tracers efficiently discriminated croplands and both
 331 geomorphic features while they did not discriminate Mediterranean forest (Mf) and the Pine
 332 afforestation (PI). Moreover, a significant enhancement was observed when combining the two types
 333 of tracers, exhibiting high discrimination between all sources (Fig. 2c).

334

335 *Figure 2. Linear discrimination analysis (LDA) graph of the sediment sources (agricultural - AG, channel bank - CB,*
 336 *Mediterranean forest - Mf, Pine forest - PI and subsoil - SS) for weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracers, elemental tracers and their*
 337 *combination. From left to right: a) weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs-Content), b) elemental tracers and c) weighted*
 338 *$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer combined with elemental tracers.*

339

340 3.2 Comparing results of weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA and elemental tracers

341 The results displayed in Fig. 2 suggest a low discrimination scenario when weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA
 342 (WFA) or elemental tracers are used separately. Following the state-of-the-art when dealing with
 343 isotopic signatures, the WFA tracers were unmixed using all long chain fatty acids as tracers. The
 344 elemental tracers and the combined datasets were unmixed after selecting the tracers following the
 345 CI, CR and CTS methods. The most discriminant and conservative solutions from the elemental
 346 tracers and the combination with the WFA tracers were selected and unmixed. As it is illustrated in
 347 Fig. 3, and as expected from the discrimination exhibited in Fig. 2, neither the elemental nor the WFA
 348 tracers individually produced reliable source apportionments, which was only achieved by combining
 349 the WFA and elemental tracers. In Fig. 3a, for example, results from unmixing with the WFA tracers
 350 showed a high dispersion and overlap between both geomorphic features (CB and SS) and AG. On
 351 the contrary, the unmixing with the elemental tracers (Fig. 3b) showed a defined peak for SS while

352 high variability and overlap between land uses. Finally, the apportionment results from the combined
 353 set of tracers (WFA and elemental tracers) (Fig. 3c) displayed well defined and narrow peaks with no
 354 significant overlap between the sources.

355

356 *Figure 3. Results of the unmixing procedure for mixture SSC-M1 with weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracers ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs-Content),*
 357 *elemental tracers and their combination for the five sediment sources (agricultural - AG, channel bank - CB, Mediterranean*
 358 *forest - Mf, Pine forest - PI and subsoil - SS). From left to right: a) weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs-Content), b)*
 359 *elemental tracers and c) weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer combined with elemental tracers.*

360

361 3.3 The effect of land management and rainfall on source apportionment changes

362 The contribution of sources to sediments at the catchment outlet varied seasonally (Fig. 4 and Table
 363 S1). The apportionment results for the individual and combined set of tracers displayed in Fig. 4
 364 indicated that channel bank (CB), agriculture (AG) and subsoils (SS) were the main contributors for
 365 most seasons with a mean contribution during the entire year of 29%, 39% and 30%, respectively.
 366 Sources characterised by a more permanent vegetation cover and low influence of human activities,
 367 such as the pine afforestation (PI) and the Mediterranean forest (Mf), showed insignificant
 368 contributions for the studied year. Regarding AG, its contribution remained similar during spring and
 369 summer (26% and 17%), with a sharp increase after autumn (95%) and decreasing again during
 370 winter. In contrast, in winter, a sharp increase of the SS was observed. On the other hand, the CB
 371 contribution was high and constant during spring and summer and decreased drastically during
 372 autumn and winter. Finally, the SS contribution was most dominant after the winter period (17%).

373 *Table S1. Mean (Avg) and standard deviation (sd) of sediment source contributions obtained via FingerPro model for*
 374 *agricultural (AG), channel bank (CB), Mediterranean forest (Mf), pine forest (PI) and subsoil (SS) to the four seasonal*

375 sediment mixture samples: Spring (SSC-M1), Summer (SSC-M2), Autumn (SSC-M3), and Winter (SSC-M4). CTS, CR and CI
 376 refer to the Consistent Tracer Selection (CTS), Consensus Ranking (CR) and Conservativeness Index (CI) methods.

ID	AG		CB		Mf		PI		SS		Selected tracers CTS + CR + CI
	Avg	sd	Avg	sd	Avg	sd	Avg	sd	Avg	sd	
Spring (SSC - M 1)	0.26	0.05	0.49	0.09	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.23	0.10	C22, C26, C28, Ca, Li, Ni
Summer (SSC - M 2)	0.17	0.07	0.46	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.32	0.07	C22, C28, C32, Bi, Cr, Ni
Autumn (SSC - M 3)	0.95	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.00	0.03	0.02	C22, C24, C30, C32, Bi
Winter (SSC - M 4)	0.18	0.04	0.19	0.08	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.60	0.12	C26, Xlf, Li, S

377

378

379 Figure 4. Mean values of sediment source (see Fig. 3 for explanation) proportions (% contribution) during the study period.
 380 Vertical black dashed lines highlight rainfall events higher than 50mm with the labels of mm of rainfall in white boxes. The
 381 brackets located at the bottom of the graph illustrate the time span since the suspended sediment collector (SSC) was
 382 installed and its collection for each season. Spring (SSC-M1), Summer (SSC-M2), Autumn (SSC-M3), and Winter (SSC-M4)
 383 represent the four sediment mixtures collected seasonally.

384 Recorded storm events could prompt source contribution changes such as the one on 2017-10-18,
 385 which likely produced the sharp autumn AG peak, or the one on 2018-01-07, which probably
 386 triggered the increased contribution of the SS source. The contribution of agricultural (AG) sources
 387 exhibited a clear pattern in accordance with the different crop stages with a sharp increase during
 388 autumn due to cereal sowing and a noticeable decline as the winter progressed and the crops began
 389 to grow. Moreover, this trend is further amplified by the coinciding occurrence of the storm event on
 390 October 18, 2017, during a period when most crops are devoid of vegetation and highly susceptible
 391 to erosion due to sowing soil disturbance. The absence of vegetation makes the soil more easily
 392 erodible, contributing to the heightened impact on agricultural sediment.

393

394 **4. DISCUSSION**

395 **4.1 Highlights and challenges of the tracer combination**

396 Findings from this research confirm previous hypothesis about the benefits of combining long-
397 chain fatty acid and elemental tracers to discriminate different land uses and geomorphic features
398 (Reiffarth et al., 2016; Lizaga et al., 2022). Combining tracers successfully separated and unmixed
399 all sediment sources. As mentioned in previous studies, overlap and large within-source variability
400 of tracer signals are considered important challenges in the application of fingerprinting models
401 (Parnell et al., 2010). This lack of discrimination is likely to result in an increased uncertainty in the
402 estimated source contributions (Phillips and Gregg, 2003; Upadhayay et al., 2017).

403 Another advantage of combining different types of tracers is that some sources of error, such as
404 low source discrimination or non-conservative processes, could be cancelled due to the selection of
405 alternative tracers. Nevertheless, this improvement in discrimination is at the expense of an increase
406 in complexity. For this reason, informative methods such as the CI, CR and CTS are suggested to
407 implement tracer selection, especially when increasing the number of tracers, resulting in over-
408 determined systems with possible distinct solutions. Thus, employing these informative methods
409 allows for the identification of an optimal set of tracers for each mixture, facilitating accurate
410 fingerprinting results.

411 Evidences from this study show that tracers with low discrimination capacity, although commonly
412 used in sediment fingerprinting studies (Vale et al., 2022), have a significant impact on the
413 apportionment results and can occasionally lead researchers to incorrect interpretations.

414 For this reason, developing and validating new techniques to combine different types of tracers is
415 of interest to enhance the accuracy of sediment fingerprinting modelling. The presented issues have
416 not been reported to date for two main reasons: i) it is not common to analyse both types of tracers
417 (isotopic and elemental tracers) in a single study either for budgetary reasons or equipment
418 availability and ii) the lack of a method to combine $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs and FAs-content into a weighted
419 elemental tracer.

420

421 4.2 Triggering factors of changes in sediment export

422 The results from this research identify soil degradation mainly due to poor past land management and
423 overgrazing and present agricultural practices as main drivers for source contribution changes in the
424 study catchment. Recent studies combining remote sensing and particle size analysis have shed light
425 on the relationship between rainfall, vegetation status, and stage on particle size variations and
426 exported mass (Lizaga et al., 2022b). While rainfall remains the predominant factor, the vegetation
427 status and crop stage also exert influence on the particle size and exported mass. In line with this
428 previous evidence, our results support that land use management and human impacts make sediments
429 available so that after the occurrence of rainfall events, sediments are washed away by runoff in the
430 sediment cascade within the hydrological system to be finally exported downstream. This trend
431 follows the general crop stages, with the highest contribution from the AG source in autumn due to
432 sowing of winter cereals and the bare soil surface. During the spring and summer seasons, the
433 contribution of channel banks (CB) remains consistently high as they serve as the closest available
434 sediment source. However, in autumn, their contribution experiences a significant decrease due to the
435 dominant input from agricultural (AG) sources, which obscures the signals from other sources. In
436 winter, the CB contribution is also reduced due to the overall stability and limited disturbance of the
437 surrounding areas, mainly characterised by the presence of croplands. This consistent relationship
438 between CB and AG contributions throughout most of the year can be attributed to the strategic
439 location of most croplands. These croplands are typically situated on fluvial terraces occupying the
440 valley floors surrounding the streams. The choice of this location for cultivating crops is influenced
441 by factors such as accessibility, the absence of steep slopes, and the presence of deeper soils (refer to
442 Fig. 1A). Thus, every process induced by the agricultural practices close to the borders of the channel
443 banks could facilitate pipping or other erosion processes that lead to rainfall-induced topless or
444 landslides of the almost vertical channel banks. This phenomenon becomes particularly evident under
445 intense storm events, as observed by Gaspar et al. (2019) during an exceptional storm event in
446 October 2012. Despite the high sediment export from agricultural sources, the CB stood out as the

447 primary contributor. This was primarily due to the sharp increase in erosive processes triggered by
448 the shear stress on the banks across the entire talus section which are the closest available sediment
449 source (Lizaga et al., 2019a).

450 As previously discussed, the presence of vegetation growth in croplands plays a crucial role in
451 stabilising channel banks throughout the year, except during extreme rainfall events. This vegetation
452 cover, coupled with the absence of tillage practices and the growth of crops, leads to a relatively
453 moderate to low contribution from both channel banks and croplands during the winter period. During
454 this time, numerous rainfall events of moderate intensity occur, causing erosion primarily in degraded
455 areas while having limited impact on the croplands or channel banks. Consequently, the primary
456 source of sediment during the winter period shifts to bare soil or degraded areas (referred to as SS),
457 surpassing contributions from other sources.

458 The low contribution of MF and PI sources is determined by the protective effect of the vegetation
459 cover, further enhanced by the terraced landscaped characteristic in the pine afforestation areas, which
460 agrees with observations in other environments (Bravo-Linares et al., 2018; Gibbs, 2008). Likely,
461 only extreme storm events that overflow the pine terraces have the capability to mobilise surface soil
462 from these well-protected surfaces and transport it into the main streams. However, during these
463 events, the amount of sediment exported is still insignificant compared to the high contribution from
464 the other sources (Lizaga et al., 2019a). Nevertheless, previous studies conducted in the area have
465 identified a significant increase in sediment contributions from the pine forests as a result of
466 clearcutting activities. This is primarily attributed to the presence of bare soil left behind during the
467 clearcutting process and the subsequent traffic of heavy machinery (Lizaga et al., 2021). These factors
468 contribute to an elevated sediment supply from the clearcut areas of harvested pine forests which
469 were not detected during the study period.

470

471 5. CONCLUSIONS

472 Despite the complexity of the study area and its homogeneous lithology, the combined use of
473 weighted fatty acids ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs and FAs-content) and elemental composition tracers successfully
474 identified the five sediment sources for seasonally collected suspended sediments. In contrast, the
475 individual use of either weighted fatty acids or elemental tracers produced inconsistent results for this
476 specific study. Therefore, employing multiple types of tracers in complex catchments is crucial to
477 reach a consensus and facilitate the identification of specific sources that would otherwise be
478 indistinguishable, despite their potentially significant contributions. Careful consideration should be
479 given when unmixing a large number of sources (> 4 sources) in complex environments to avoid
480 over/underestimation of sparsely discriminated sources.

481 The results of this research highlight the dominant role of agricultural practices and high storm
482 events in driving the spatiotemporal variability of sediment export. Apportionment results provide
483 evidence of the severe soil loss caused by land degradation and the impact of bare soil in
484 Mediterranean agroecosystems despite its relatively small surface coverage. These findings suggest
485 the possibility of implementing targeted restoration strategies without sacrificing the identification of
486 sediment provenance from geofoms or land covers. By encompassing multiple potential sources and
487 obtaining more precise results, this methodology opens up opportunities for the implementation and
488 monitoring of targeted restoration strategies with greater efficacy.

489 The presented methods have been implemented in the R programming language and will be
490 published in the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) and GitHub repositories within the
491 FingerPro package. Furthermore, in adherence to the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility,
492 interoperability, and reuse), the data required to replicate the results and figures presented in this
493 manuscript will be made available on a public repository.

494

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720 **Figure captions**

721 Figure 3. Location of the Barués catchment in the central part of the Ebro Basin (NE Spain).
722 3D map of the catchment and its surroundings. A-E pictures of the different land use, A)
723 agricultural land use occupying the valley floors and deeply incised stream surrounded by
724 landslides (topples), B) Mediterranean forest, C) pine afforestation, D) degraded soil, E) river
725 bank, and F) eroded crop after a high intensity rainfall.

726

727 Figure 4. Linear discrimination analysis (LDA) graph of the sediment sources (agricultural -
728 AG, channel bank - CB, Mediterranean forest – Mf, Pine forest - PI and subsoil - SS) for
729 weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracers, elemental tracers and their combination. From left to right: a)
730 weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs -Content), b) elemental tracers and c) weighted
731 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer combined with elemental tracers.

732

733 Figure 3. Results of the unmixing procedure for mixture SSC-M1 with weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA
734 tracers ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs-Content), elemental tracers and their combination for the five
735 sediment sources (agricultural - AG, channel bank - CB, Mediterranean forest – Mf, Pine
736 forest - PI and subsoil - SS). From left to right: a) weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FAs, FAs-
737 Content), b) elemental tracers and c) weighted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -FA tracer combined with elemental
738 tracers.

739

740 Figure 4. Mean values of sediment source (see Fig. 3 for explanation) proportions (%
741 contribution) during the study period. Vertical black dashed lines highlight rainfall events
742 higher than 50mm with the labels of mm of rainfall in white boxes. The brackets located at
743 the bottom of the graph illustrate the time span since the suspended sediment collector (SSC)
744 was installed and its collection for each season. Spring (SSC-M1), Summer (SSC-M2),
745 Autumn (SSC-M3), and Winter (SSC-M4) represent the four sediment mixtures collected
746 seasonally.

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